

EARTH SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract

Harmful gases that negatively affect human health and pollute the atmosphere cause serious damage not only to human health, but also to the ecosystem and climate. In order to prevent atmospheric pollution, it is important to use alternative energy sources, promote public transport and reduce industrial emissions. Atmospheric pollution causes respiratory diseases, nervous system diseases, cardiovascular system disorders, mental and physical diseases in children, and a number of serious organ diseases.

Keywords: atmospheric pollution, human health, harmful gases

In our modern era, protecting the environment (soil, water, air) from pollution is of great importance in ensuring ecological balance. The problems caused by global climate change and the annual growth of the ozone hole in human health are proof that health directly depends on the events occurring in the environment. Atmospheric pollution causes not only human health, but also changes in the entire natural ecosystem, causing significant changes in plant and animal species. The efficient use of natural resources and the elimination of sources that pollute the atmosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, and lithosphere are among the main issues facing us. For this purpose, all countries of the world are implementing various measures to combat this.

In countries with different levels of development, the identification of substances that change the composition of the air in connection with the development of

industry, and the awareness-raising and combat work carried out to eliminate them are commendable.

Work progress

Drought caused by climate change, reduction of water resources, reduction of forest belts, change in the distribution area of flora and fauna, increase in bacteriological diseases affecting human health, etc. are the most urgent problems caused by atmospheric pollution. Air pollution leads to an increase in respiratory diseases, heart diseases, and even psychological diseases. Regular monitoring of air quality, maintaining it stable, developing new projects to identify and prevent pollution sources, and implementing extensive awareness-raising activities are the most important steps.

Let's look at the description of indicators characterizing atmospheric air protection and harmful effects in Azerbaijan in the last 3 years:

Table 1.

	2021	2022	2023
	457	480	442
Stationary source pollution (thousand tons)			
Stationary source emissions (%)	66	67	67
Transport (automobile) pollution	723	772	821
Vehicle emissions (%)	82	83	85
Transport (automobile) emissions per capita, kg	72	76	81

Based on the table, it can be concluded that the most serious source of pollution is road transport. Compared to 2021, the amount of harmful substances emitted into the air from cars in 2023 reached 821 thousand tons and continues its upward trend. The per capita pollutant from road transport also increased to 81 kg, which poses a serious risk to public health.

Although a certain decrease in pollution from stationary sources was observed in 2023 (from 480 thousand tons to 442 thousand tons), the total share is still high.

Steps that must be taken to prevent these pollutions, which pose a serious threat to human health:

Scheme 1.

Harmful gases that negatively affect human health and pollute the atmosphere cause serious damage not only to human health, but also to the ecosystem and climate. In order to prevent atmospheric pollution, it is important to use alternative energy sources, promote public transport and reduce industrial emissions. At-

mospheric pollution causes respiratory diseases, nervous system diseases, cardiovascular system disorders, mental and physical diseases in children, and a number of serious organ diseases.

Amount of harmful gases that negatively affect human health and pollute the atmosphere, thousand tons

Scheme 2.

This diagram presents the amounts of the main gases that have a warming effect for 2021, 2022 and 2023 (in thousand tons).

Conclusion and suggestions

Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) - a significant decrease is observed in 2022.

In 2023, there is a re-increase in the amount, but it does not reach the 2021 level.

Nitrous Oxide (N₂O) - a sharp decrease in the amount in 2022. A slight increase is observed in 2023.

Methane (CH₄) - there is a very sharp jump (about 2.7 times increase) especially in 2023. This is a serious danger signal, because methane is a more powerful greenhouse gas than CO₂ (in the short term).

Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) - there is a very serious decrease in 2022, but it returned to its previous level in 2023.

The increase in methane is the most concerning.

Although CO₂ levels are decreasing, it is still a major cause of climate change.

Nitrous oxide and HFCs need to be controlled.

Measures such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, and improved transport systems are essential to reduce emissions.

In 2025, significant steps were taken to protect human health. Most importantly, the **78th World Health Assembly (WHA78)** held in Geneva marked a key

event. Let's take a look at the resolution and its significance.

Scheme 3.

During this assembly, a new resolution titled **"Promoting and Prioritizing an Integrated Lung Health Approach"** was adopted, drawing attention to human health in many countries and initiating important measures in this direction.

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